

MooringSense – GA 851703

Mooring System Integrity Management through Monitoring, Digital Twin and Control Technologies for Cost Reduction and Increased Efficiency

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Integrity Management Strategy Definition

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Executive Summary

The MooringSense project aims to reducing Operational Expenditure (OPEX) and increasing efficiency of floating offshore wind turbines through the development of efficient risk-based integrity management strategies for mooring systems based on a cost effective and reliable on-line monitoring technology and digital twin. Currently, integrity management for Mooring Lines is based around time-based inspections and does not account for the location, type of damage or risk. Given the high cost of offshore operations (inspection, maintenance, repairs) it is of vital importance that a cost-effective integrity management strategy is developed to keep OPEX at an acceptable level.

This deliverable details the advantages of using a risk-based methodology and goes on to develop a Risk Based integrity management strategy specific to MooringSense, to optimise inspection activity and reduce OPEX. Risk Based Inspection (RBI) identifies the components and areas in a mooring system of greatest risk and focuses inspection efforts on these areas. Risk Based Inspection is also able to detail the risks from a safety/health/environment perspective and/or from an economic standpoint. From this an optimised approach to inspection planning can be taken, with appropriate inspection intervals assigned which are based on risk.

The degree of understanding of mooring integrity risk during the life of an asset, increases over time as more data from inspection and the digital twin becomes available. The assessment of mooring risk is, therefore, an ongoing activity with the level of detail increasing throughout the life cycle, and risk must be periodically reassessed over the lifetime of the windfarm, from design phase through to decommissioning.

To develop the integrity management strategy, all potential threats and damage mechanisms that a mooring line may be subject to through its entire lifecycle have been identified. The mooring line is also segmented to identify specific areas of higher risk. The risk profile will not be uniform along the Mooring Line and not all degradation mechanisms are seen at all water depths.

Risk can be assessed quantitatively or qualitatively. The risk level in MooringSense has been assessed qualitatively because degradation mechanisms associated with Mooring Lines are often complex and difficult to model. Fully quantitative RBI assessment is also data heavy and laborious and often does not further reduce risk nor results in better outcomes. The risk level is a combination of the likelihood of failure and the consequence of failure, and then the risk is evaluated using a risk matrix, to target targeting inspection to critical areas that require attention. This forms an initial risk ranking and inspection plan.

The strategy then utilises the MooringSense digital twin, to inform inspection activities. The Structural Health Monitoring system and Remaining Useful Life tools are integrated into the strategy to inform the risk quantifying process. These provide continuous, online information, to flag integrity threats or degraded condition before an inspection would. The baseline inspection plan can then be altered according to digital twin data.

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List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

Term	Description
API	American Petroleum Institute
CVI	Close Visual Inspection
DNV	Det Norske Veritas
DT	Digital Twin
FAD	Failure Assessment Diagram
FFS	Fitness for Service
FOW	Floating Offshore Wind
FOWT	Floating Offshore Wind Turbine
GVI	General Visual Inspection
IM	Integrity Management
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LCoE	Levelized Cost of Energy
MIC	Microbiologically Induced Corrosion
MIM	Mooring Integrity Management
MPI	Magnetic Particle Inspection
NDT	Non-Destructive Testing
O&G	Oil and Gas
O&M	Operations and Maintenance
OPEX	Operational Expenditure
PLOCAN	Plataforma Oceánica de Canarias (The Oceanic Platform of the Canary Islands)
QA/QC	Quality Assurance/Quality Control
RBI	Risk Based Inspection
ROM	Reduced Order Model
ROV	Remotely Operated Vehicle
RP	Recommended Practice
RUL	Remaining Useful Life
SATH	Swinging Around Twin Hull

SHM	Structural Health Monitoring
SIF	Stress Intensity Factor
UT	Ultrasonic Thickness
UV	Ultraviolet
WP	Work Package

1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose and scope

The purpose of this integrity management strategy definition document is to define and explain how the integrity of the mooring system as part of the SATH concept development will be applied and managed from the initial stages of the development through to end of life. This document highlights the required key performance parameters obtained through the DT sensors and simulations and their effect of the risk, remaining life, and availability. This information is used to decipher the most effective mode of mitigating the risk through either inspection, mitigating works, or altering the performance of the turbine through the control algorithm.

The resulting effective integrity management strategy reduces OPEX through optimizing inspection and maintenance whilst looking to increase the operational lifespan of assets while simultaneously managing the risks posed for any given time/scenario.

1.2 Intended audience / Classification

This document is intended for all project partners, WP leaders and WP participants. The document is not intended for use outside the project, it is therefore classified as a confidential document. *A public version of this document will also be available as deliverable D6.2 (ref).*

1.3 Application documents

Inputs from the following documents were used as a source of information for preparing this document:

Table 1.1: Application documents

REF	Document
AD-01	Grant Agreement – 851703 - MooringSense
AD-02	Consortium Agreement – MooringSense

1.4 Reference Documents

The following documents were used as reference for preparing this report:

Table 1.2 Reference Documents

REF	Document
RD-01	D2.1 Integrity Management Technologies
RD-02	D2.3 Reference Case and Set-Up of the Baseline
RD-03	D2.4 Digital Twin Architecture
RD-04	D2.5 Specifications and validation definition
RD-05	D3.3 Numerical Modelling – Degradation and Failure

RD-06	D3.4 Remaining Useful Life Prediction Tool
RD-07	D5.1 Structural Health Monitoring Solution Definition
RD-08	D6.3 Close Loop Control Strategies Definition

1.5 Document structure

This document is structured as follows:

- **Section 2** gives a general introduction and background into integrity management, current practices in floating offshore wind integrity management and current guidelines and standards
- **Section 3** gives a summary of the SATH concept from the reference case, which the strategy will be based around
- **Section 4** describes Risk Based Integrity Management, the data requirements for this, and describes the benefits of qualitative and quantitative approaches to RBI
- **Section 5** details the identification of relevant damage mechanisms and gives an example segmentation of the mooring system
- **Section 6** describes different types of inspection
- **Section 7** explains the importance of a baseline inspection
- **Section 8** gives the criteria and methodology by which the risk will be assessed, including criteria for likelihood of failure and consequence of failure, and includes a risk matrix for quantifying risk
- **Section 9** is the Risk Assessment itself, set out per damage mechanism and for both the Chain Catenary Solution and Hybrid Line Solution
- **Section 10** gives a summary of the results from the risk assessment in Section 9
- **Section 11** is the full inspection plan, including how to optimise the inspection frequency
- **Section 12** details how event-based inspections should be approached
- **Section 13** describes the process for risk re-assessment following examination
- **Section 14** describes the requirements for short- and long-term response planning, and general mitigation, intervention, and repair procedures
- **Section 15** integrates the MooringSense tools into the integrity management strategy, detailing how Tools such as the RUL and SHM system can be used to inform integrity management
- **Section 16** is a summary of the report

2. General

The MooringSense concept aims to reduce operational costs of offshore floating wind and increase efficiency; through the development of an efficient risk-based integrity management (IM) strategy for mooring systems, based on an affordable and reliable on-line monitoring technology.

This requires the development of a new and innovative IM strategy, that takes advantage of mooring systems' updated condition information, provided by a Digital Twin (DT) and innovative monitoring technologies, to allow the implementation of a risk-based IM plan and more holistic control strategies to reduce OPEX and increase energy production of Floating Offshore Wind (FOW) farms. MooringSense will contribute to a reduction of uncertainties that in the long run will lead to a reduction of Operations and Maintenance (O&M) costs, by reducing the needs of frequent inspections and by reducing loss of production and downtime.

IM is a continuous process applied for the purpose of demonstrating the fitness-for-service (FFS) of a mooring system from installation, through the operational life and potential life extension, to decommissioning. It is therefore crucial to consider integrity management a long term and iterative process.

Integrity control activities can be generally performed in different stages of the lifecycle of a FOW farm and can be classified as follows:

- Baseline Inspection
- Planned Integrity Control Activities
- Unscheduled Inspections

Specific to the MooringSense concept is the use of inspection/integrity control activities driven by data from the DT and structural health monitoring (SHM) system.

Figure 2.1 Integrity Management Process

Effective implementation of an IM strategy delivers improved safety and risk reduction, environmental assurance, optimized maintenance and inspection activities, increased service life and enhanced performance and profit.

2.1 Current Integrity Practices in Offshore Floating Wind

Although IM principles have been used for many years within the Oil and Gas (O&G) industry with huge success, FOW IM is not an established sector.

The effective inspection solutions currently used in O&G, including time-based inspections for all mooring lines, are unaffordable for FOW, due to the quantity of mooring lines in a FOW farm which require inspection. Additionally, short inspection intervals for mooring lines are typically required, with O&G industry standards stating requirements of around 1-5 years. The existing monitoring solutions are expensive and have shown limited reliability and robustness.

There is great variance in the frequency of mooring inspections between operators within O&G. The inspection schedule may be mandated to comply with legislative requirements which may be different around the world. In a lot of cases, International Industry Standards are a recommendation on inspection frequency rather than a mandatory requirement. This results in great variances as operators try to minimize the required inspections to reduce their operating costs.

Robust sets of failure rates for FOW farms to guide inspection intervals are also not available, as the infancy of the technology means there are few FOW farms currently operational. The FOW farms which are operational are also early in their operational life that the failure rates observed are not adequate to fully guide the requirement for inspection.

Increased complexity and higher dynamics due to coupled behavior of a FOW turbine can also mean that high numbers of mooring line failures can be expected over the design life, resulting in high O&M costs. Therefore, innovation is urgently required in the FOW Industry, which the MooringSense Project aims to address.

2.1.1 Existing Guidelines

There is no specific guidance currently available for IM for Mooring Systems of Floating Offshore Wind Turbines (FOWT), nor IM strategies that integrate the use of a digital twin or any of the tools the MooringSense Project employs, due to the nascency of the technologies.

Several documents surrounding the topic of mooring integrity are available; however, they all specifically tailored towards the oil and gas industry. FOWT mooring parameters are not the same as oil and gas mooring parameters (due to smaller floater sizes, wind turbine induced loads, shallower mooring depths, and redundancy requirements) and so as discussed previously, existing data for mooring lines is of limited relevance to FOWT systems.

Listed below are the current most relevant documents available:

- API RP 2I In Service Inspection of Mooring Hardware for Floating Structures
- API RP 2MIM Mooring Integrity Management
- ISO/DIS 19901-7 Station keeping system for floating offshore structures and mobile offshore units
- API 580/581 Risk Based Inspection
- DNV-RP-E308 Mooring Integrity Management

International Standards do not mandate a specific inspection interval, however API RP 2I recommends a maximum interval between major inspections, which depends on how many years the line has been in service. These have been reported in Table 2.1 for chain and wire ropes.

Table 2.1 Chain and Wire Rope inspection intervals

	Years in service	Maximum Interval between Inspection
Chain	0 - 3	36 Months
	4 - 10	24 Months
	Over 10	8 Months
Wire Rope	0 - 2	18 Months
	3 - 5	12 Months
	Over 5	9 Months

3. Summary of the System

A reference case and set up conditions for the baseline scenario to be used on the development of the MooringSense project has been defined in Deliverable 2.3 (RD-02). The IM strategy has been developed with this reference case in mind, however with the potential to also be applied to other FOW farms with the same MooringSense technologies.

In Deliverable 2.3 (RD-02) a general technical description of the SATH Platform is presented with the potential locations to conduct the station keeping design and, simultaneously, to establish a common frame of comparison.

This document is aimed to provide a Reference Case to the design of FOWT station keeping systems focused on the SATH Technology to:

- Identify the main degradation mechanisms and failure modes of the mooring configurations,
- Estimate the LCoE breakdown for the whole FOWT,
- Define a representative set of operational scenarios and events and,
- Define the KPIs to measure the success of the project development.

The two reference cases chose are Buchan Deep on the east coast of Scotland, and PLOCAN, the Oceanic Platform of the Canary Islands, Spain, multipurpose technical-scientific service infrastructure that provides support for research, technological development, and innovation in the marine and maritime sectors. The SATH platform is moored with a 6-line spread mooring system with an external turret for weather vaning. Two mooring line configurations are subject to study within the Project (all chain and hybrid chain-rope-chain), as well as the two different locations (Scotland and the Canary Islands).

The reference cases vary in terms of their met-ocean and geotechnical data. Full details of these can also be found in Deliverable 2.3 (RD-02).

4. Risk Based Integrity Management

Risk Based Inspection (RBI) is the process of developing a scheme of inspection based on knowledge of the risk of failure. This is the combination of an assessment of the likelihood (probability) of failure due to damage, deterioration, or degradation, with an assessment of the consequences of such a failure. Two-dimensional (i.e. likelihood and consequence) risk ranking is subsequently used to establish effective inspection intervals, scopes, and methods of Inspection/examination.

RBI represents the next generation of inspection approaches and interval setting, recognizing that the ultimate goal of inspection is the safety and reliability of operating facilities. RBI focuses specifically on the equipment and associated deterioration mechanisms representing the most risk to the windfarm. In focusing on risks and their mitigation, RBI provides a better linkage between the mechanisms that lead to equipment failure and the inspection approaches that will effectively reduce the associated risks.

The process optimises Inspection and / or monitoring in a dynamic way, ensuring inspection resources are focused on the areas of greater concern, and provides a methodology for determining the optimum combination of inspection methods and frequencies. Items with high probability and high consequence (i.e., high risk) are given a higher priority for Inspection than items that are high probability but for which Failure has low consequences.

An impending failure and its consequences are not prevented or changed by RBI unless additional mitigating actions are taken. Inspection is an initiator for actions such as the repair or replacement of deteriorating equipment, or a change to the operating conditions. By identifying potential problems, RBI increases the chances that mitigating actions will be taken, and thereby reduces the frequency of Failure.

The Mooring Sense IM strategy is going to use a Risk Based approach, instead of the current time-based methodology. The current time-based methodology employed in FOW farms means the inspection frequency, inspection methods and locations inspected have little consideration with regards to the age, function, or likely damage.

Figure 4.1 shows how a typical RBI program over time reduces both the overall risk and the level of inspection activity required.

Figure 4.1 Management of Risk Using RBI (1)

As shown in Figure 4.1, the risk cannot be reduced to zero solely by inspection efforts. The residual risk factors for loss of production include, but are not limited to, the following:

- a) Human error.
- b) Natural disasters.
- c) External events (e.g., collisions or falling objects).
- d) Secondary effects from nearby units.
- e) Consequential effects from associated equipment in the same unit.
- f) Deliberate acts (e.g., sabotage).
- g) Fundamental limitations of inspection method.
- h) Design errors.
- i) Unknown mechanisms of deterioration.

Despite this residual risk, RBI has proven within the O&G sector to be the best approach for IM.

The risk assessment process is shown in Figure 4.2. The information gained from this process is used to identify:

- the type of damage that may potentially be present
- where such damage could occur
- the rate at which such damage might evolve
- where failure would give rise to danger

Figure 4.2 Schematic of the Risk Assessment Process (1)

4.1 Data for Risk Based Inspection

Fundamental to the RBI Process is an adequate record of essential data relating to the plant. RBI involves continuous review and monitoring of data (inspection, operational, fabrication, etc.), re-evaluating the condition and anticipated condition of the assets. This essential data provides the RBI team with a basis on which to judge the continued safe operation. If accurate or complete records have not been maintained, then the assessment will inevitably become conservative which could indicate the risks to be higher than if more information were available.

One important aspect in the use of such data is that, wherever possible, all data should be validated. It is best to treat hearsay, assumptions, or unconfirmed data with caution and make due allowances for uncertainty in the risk assessment.

The original design and construction drawings and inspection reports of equipment are essential to assess many aspects relating to its structural integrity. This information can be treated as a 'fingerprint' against which the results of all subsequent inspections can be compared. For example, if a vessel is considered liable to corrode and the initial material thickness of the vessel is not known, then the corrosion rate cannot be calculated with any degree of accuracy.

Previous inspection reports enable trends in the deterioration of equipment to be established. Trends can then be extrapolated for the assessment of the limits to continued safe operation. It is important that all previous inspection reports are considered and not only the most recent.

Documentation associated with any mooring line repairs or modifications should be reviewed to ensure that the work has been carried out satisfactorily and in accordance with relevant standards etc. The reasons for the repair or modification should also be reviewed to ascertain the effect on probability of failure.

4.2 Quantitative vs Qualitative RBI

There are three main methodologies of RBI assessment that can be conducted, at varying levels of complexity. These types are as follows:

1. Qualitative
2. Semi-Quantitative, (a methodology which uses aspects of both qualitative and quantitative)
3. Full Quantitative

The choice of approach is dependent on multiple variables such as:

- a) Objective of the study.
- b) Number of facilities and equipment items to study.
- c) Available resources.
- d) Study time frame.
- e) Complexity of facilities and processes.
- f) Nature and quality of available data.

Each methodology provides a systematic way to assess the overall risk, identify areas that may be of concern, identify applicable damage mechanisms which have the potential to degrade the system and develop a prioritized list for more in depth inspection or analysis.

Each also develops a risk ranking measure to be utilised for evaluating separately the likelihood of failure and the potential consequence of failure. These two values are then combined to establish the risk

ranking. Use of expert opinion / engineering judgement will typically be included in most risk assessments, however this is minimised when using a fully quantitative methodology.

For MooringSense, a Qualitative approach has been used. This is due to multiple reasons:

- Degradation mechanisms associated with Mooring Lines are often complex and difficult to model, and therefore a fully quantitative model is unrealistic.
- Full quantitative RBI assessment is data heavy and laborious, with a vast amount of both design and operational data required to complete the assessment.
- For the majority of FOW farms currently, there is a lack of reliable data for an accurate assessment.
- Qualitative analysis may be easier to start with, requires less data and it is easier to communicate outside the RBI team.
- Quantitative RBI often does not further reduce risk nor results in better outcomes.

As experience is gained in the FOW industry, it is envisioned the IM strategy will develop into Semi-Quantitative approach. Semi-quantitative is a term that describes any approach that has aspects derived from both the qualitative and quantitative approaches. It gains the major benefits of both quantitative and qualitative approaches (e.g., speed of the qualitative and rigor of the quantitative). It is important to note that quantitative is not seen as competing with qualitative methods, rather as complimentary approaches that can be blended to reach an optimal strategy.

5. Developing the Integrity Strategy for Mooring Sense

The risk-based approach proposed for MooringSense in this document attempts to quantify the level of risk posed to the mooring system. This is done by firstly understanding all the possible failure modes, damage and deterioration mechanisms, their expected location on the mooring line, their criticality to safe, low risk operation, and how each damage mechanism impacts the probability and consequences of failure.

When unexpected damage is detected, the IM plan should provide the basis for decision making. This requires a good understanding of the severity of the damage and the active damage mechanisms.

5.1 Damage Mechanisms

The first step of an IM strategy is to define the various damage and degradation mechanisms expected to be active within the mooring systems of floating installations in the specified site. A good understanding of the applicable degradation mechanisms is vital to the safe, low risk operation of offshore assets, and is key to the design and to implement an efficient IM plan, including the selection and scheduling of inspections.

Understanding potential damage is important, not only for determining the probability of failure, but also for the selection of the appropriate inspection intervals to coincide with both the level of risk as well as the project's financial and operational objectives.

The process used for identifying deterioration mechanisms for Mooring Lines should be conducted in a wide ranging and systematic manner. It is more effective if it involves experienced staff from different disciplines rather than being the work of a single person. Acceptable processes could include combinations of the following:

- Review of the specific FWF's history and information from previous inspections
- Review of experience across similar industries
- Expert elicitation of knowledge of structural integrity and materials
- Use of checklists and mechanism descriptions
- Computer based expert systems

The damage mechanisms seen in offshore floating wind are not new concepts. Mooring lines (chain and synthetic) are widely found in O&G, however the rate at which these damage mechanisms contribute to failure in offshore floating wind are currently unknown, due to the nascency of the technology and lack of data publicly available.

The identification of damage mechanisms applicable to the Mooring lines in the reference cases for MooringSense has been consolidated through a combination of previous experience and literature.

These damage modes are explained in full detail in Deliverable 2.1 (RD-01).

Table 5.1 below summarises damage mechanisms for both chain and synthetic mooring lines.

Table 5.1 Damage Mechanisms in Chain and Synthetic Mooring Lines

Chain Mooring Lines	Synthetic Mooring Lines
Corrosion (General, Pitting and MIC)	Core Damage/External Damage (Abrasion, Cutting, Particle Ingress)
Interlink Wear	UV Radiation
Straight Tension Fatigue	Axial Stiffness
Out of Plane Bending Fatigue	Compression Fatigue
Marine Growth	Marine Growth
Mechanical Damage	Tension Fatigue
	Elongation (Slack Line)

5.2 Segmentation

An effective IM Strategy will segment the Mooring Line, as the risk profile will not be uniform along the Mooring Line and that the degree and type of risk mitigations required, will vary. This enables an increase of inspection efforts on segments that demonstrate higher levels of risk.

Not all degradation mechanisms are seen at all water depths, and applicable for every segment. For example, corrosion is not found in synthetic ropes, and seabed contact is only found in the chain near the seabed. Segmenting the mooring line ensures inspection efforts are targeted only where the degradation mechanism is possible.

Therefore, to address this requirement, the Mooring Line will be divided into segments based on the Mooring Line configuration. Typically, the segmentation/division of a mooring line into segments is driven by discontinuities such as different line properties (chain, wire, diameter, rope material, etc.) and the presence of clump weights or buoys. It may also be segmented according to water depths.

Different areas of the windfarm may also be segmented if they are subject to different risks such as being near a shipping route or exposed to different weather conditions. In both reference cases, it is assumed the external risks associated with each floating system are the same across the entirety of the windfarm and will remain constant over the design life, therefore this type of segmentation is not seen in this strategy.

Segmentation is dynamic, so it shall be modified if a major change arises in the criteria above (i.e., change of population in one area, change of operational parameters etc.).

It is up to the individual windfarm operators to define the exact limits, but a suggested segmentation for Mooring Sense is detailed in Section 5.2.1 and 5.2.2 for both the Catenary and Hybrid Systems.

5.2.1 Chain Catenary Solution

Figure 5.1 Schematic of an example Segmentation for the Mooring Sense Chain Catenary Concept

Table 5.2 Segmentation description

Number	Segment
1	Anchor to first chain link
2	Seabed Chain
3	Chain that is suspended in the water up to the splash zone
4	Chain in Splash-Zone
5	Fixed link of chain attached to and including Dual Axis Connector to Platform

5.2.2 Hybrid Solution

Figure 5.2 Schematic of an example Segmentation for the Mooring Sense Hybrid Concept

For the hybrid solution, due to the degradation mechanisms differing between material types, the mooring line is required to be further segmented. id

Table 5.3 Segmentation Description

Number	Segment
1	Anchor to first chain link
2	Second Chain Link from Anchor up to Synthetic Rope
3	Last fixed link from chain and connector from chain to synthetic rope
4	Synthetic Rope
5	Connector from synthetic rope to first fixed link of chain
6	Chain
7	Clump Weight
8	Chain from clump weight up to the platform
9	Fixed link of chain attached to and including Dual Axis Connector to Platform

6. Inspection

In FOW and in the Mooring Sense's use case, mooring systems are not to be retrieved for carrying out periodic inspections. Consequently, inspections must be performed in situ and they will rely on limited diver access and/or ROV inspections.

There are several approaches to mooring system inspection, they vary in effectiveness, cost, and suitability. The most popular inspection method is visual, this is due to its relative simplicity and comparatively low costs.

D2.1 Mooring System IM Technologies (RD-01) details the different types of inspection and their advantages and limitations.

Inspection is only effective if the inspection technique chosen is sufficient for detecting the deterioration mechanism and its severity. As an example, spot thickness readings on a mooring would be considered to have little or no benefit if the deterioration mechanism results in fatigue and cracks.

The selection and usage of the appropriate inspection tools and techniques can be optimized to cost effectively and safely reduce risk. If the inspection activities are executed effectively by well-trained and qualified inspectors, the expected risk management should be obtained.

For the IM strategy, the most suitable type of inspection for each threat has been identified. This is based on what is required to be assessed and/or measured and where along the line it is likely to be found.

7. Baseline Inspection

A baseline inspection survey is commonly performed prior to start up or, in some cases, within the first year of operation for offshore assets. It is intended to confirm the manufacturing and installation quality, conformance to design requirements and initial integrity, including confirmation of the predicted effectiveness of the cathodic protection system. It is the first inspection stage, and it is useful to provide a reference point for future inspections.

For the MooringSense reference case, it is proposed to perform a full line inspection of all Mooring Lines in the wind farm within the first 3 months of operation. This will provide an initial dataset to guide the inspection planning and IM process, as well as vital data for the Structural Health Monitoring System (SHM) and DT. Additionally, performing a baseline inspection within early operation will detect manufacturing and installation faults within the warranty period. This means replacement can be organised at minimal or no cost to the operator.

Mooring Chain damage can occur at multiple points once the chain has gone through Quality Assurance and Quality Control (QA/QC) in the manufacturing facility, from when being transported on land, to loading onto the boat, and in installation itself. The only way to ensure these are identified early on is a full inspection early in operation.

Additionally, a baseline inspection is important also for effective implementation of the MooringSense digital twin and SHM System technology. The SHM works by comparing two states: a reference one (which known as 'healthy') and a second state of the as found condition based upon inspection information and operational data. The SHM system detects if the platform is moving in a different way compared to similar environmental and operational conditions observed in the past when the platform is known to be healthy or undamaged - this is what is known as a semi-supervised situation. Which basically is that the system knows when the mooring system was healthy. The new data is compared against the data from that healthy period. If there is no difference in the trend of the movement between both states, no damage is assumed to have occurred due to the movement. In a purely data driven SHM system, as is used in the MooringSense project, the reference state will be obtained from the measured data obtained in operation. The baseline inspection is therefore crucial to provide the initial 'healthy' reference point for the SHM system.

Without a baseline inspection, an event of design / fabrication error, would not be detected by the SHM. The state (with the design/ fabrication error) would be considered as the reference healthy state by the SHM system.

The cost of a baseline inspection survey of all mooring lines is reasonably high and unfortunately unavoidable at present. However, the benefits (as detailed above) of this survey being completed within the initial 3 months of operation out-weigh the initial cost and can lead to more cost savings in the future as less maintenance / inspection is required. When technology develops in future, a baseline inspection may be able to be bypassed by using a well calibrated model of each FOWT, as the digital twin could estimate the behaviour of the FOWT and compare it with the measured one. If differences arise, the DT could detect that something is wrong, and a more directed inspection campaign can be implemented. Different simulations could potentially also be done modifying the model to try to identify the potential damaged areas. It will always be imperative to back up any simulated defects / damaged areas from the DT by carrying out inspections of the proposed damaged area.

A full description of the SHM System is found in Deliverable 5.1 (RD-06). The details of how the SHM system is integrated into the overall MooringSense IM Strategy can be found in Section 15.5.

After the baseline plan is complete, the inspection plan can then be followed. This is detailed in Section 11.

8. Assessing Risk

The need for inspection is determined, in the first instance, where a defect may give rise to danger with adverse consequences from failure. The frequency and nature of inspection is subsequently determined by the assessed probability of failure. Thus, an RBI strategy requires knowledge of both the consequences and probability of failure.

As discussed previously, the MooringSense project will be using a qualitative approach to the risk assessment. Qualitative schemes assess the likelihood of failure descriptively, using terms such as very low, low, medium, high, or very high. Such terms are of little use unless criteria for the descriptive categories are defined.

Qualitative assessments should first establish the amount and quality of information that is known about the equipment. The likelihood of failure increases without adequate information and where there is uncertainty. Providing sufficient information exists, an assessment is then made of the level of threat to fitness-for-service in the future. Among the key factors to consider are the uncertainties in the current knowledge, the variability of deterioration rate, and the possibility of secondary failures and other credible events that could affect the equipment's integrity.

This section will provide details on how the overall risk level is to be calculated for MooringSense, based upon applicable damage mechanisms and their Likelihood to failure against what the consequence would be to the asset, should a failure occur.

8.1 Likelihood of Failure

Assessing the likelihood of a failure is an important part of effective risk analyses, and in a qualitative risk assessment is decided by looking at the potential damage mechanisms it could be susceptible to, a general frequency of failures (if available), and management system factors, such as availability of historical data.

Table 8.1 gives the likelihood to failure categories and descriptions of what events would typically fit these categories. This has been developed specifically for MooringSense, adapted from best industry practices such as API 580 (1).

Table 8.1 Likelihood to Failure Scoring and Criteria

	Likelihood to Failure	Description
1	Very Low	<p>Failure is not expected</p> <p>Full operating history and records of effective previous inspections available. Loading and operating conditions known, monitored, and controlled. Deterioration rate known and monitored. Design etc. known.</p> <p>No potential for deterioration, damage, defects, or degradation, identified by assessment and none detected in previous inspection. No threat to design/FFS margins.</p>
2	Low	<p>Never heard of in the industry</p> <p>Operating history or inspection records not fully complete.</p>

		<p>Loading and operating conditions known. Deterioration rate estimated within narrow limits. Design etc. known.</p> <p>Potential for deterioration, damage, defects, or degradation identified by assessment but none detected by previous inspection. No threat to design/FFS margins predicted.</p>
3	Medium	<p>An accident has occurred in the industry</p> <p>Operating history or inspection records reasonably complete, Loading, and operating conditions known. Deterioration rate estimated within broad limits. Design etc. known.</p> <p>Deterioration, damage, defects, or degradation identified by assessment and/or detected by previous inspection. Assessment of deterioration indicates comfortable design/FFS margins in hand.</p>
4	High	<p>Has been experienced by most operators</p> <p>Operating history incomplete. Previous inspection limited in coverage effectiveness. Degradation rate uncertain. Design etc. known.</p> <p>Deterioration, damage, defects, or degradation identified by assessment and detected by previous inspection. Assessment of deterioration indicates that design/FFS margins could be close to acceptable limits.</p>
5	Very High	<p>Occurs several times per year</p> <p>Operating history unknown. Records of previous inspections unavailable. Loading and operating conditions unknown. Deterioration rate unknown. Design, material, or fabrication unknown.</p> <p>Deterioration, damage, defects, or degradation identified by assessment and detected by previous inspection. Assessment of deterioration predicts design/FFS limits to have been exceeded.</p>

8.2 Consequence

Typically, there are three criteria that can be considered when assessing the consequence of failure:

1. Health and Safety of Personnel - injury or harm to physical or psychological health
2. Financial/Economic Consequence - damage to property (assets) or loss of production
3. Reputational - employees and third parties. This includes the liabilities arising from injuries and property damage to third parties including the cross liabilities that may arise between the interdependent company groups.

Consequence of failure categories cannot be directly drawn from best practice examples in O&G standards, as these are largely based around loss of containment and the resulting environmental impact. The risk to human life is also typically less in offshore wind, as unlike many O&G facilities, the

wind farm is predominantly unmanned, and personnel are only at risk when carrying out inspection and maintenance activities.

The financial risks involved with a failure to the FOW are not fully known due to the lack of failures which have been seen within the FOW industry, however the operators should be able to provide information around the losses occurred when the FOWT is shut down and the estimates can be developed based upon the type of failure that had occurred.

Table 8.2 provides examples of consequence of failure, whether this be of consequence to the mooring system itself or to health and safety of personnel. Typically, when looking at an event with multiple consequences (e.g., Medium health and safety consequence but High consequence to the Mooring System itself), whichever is the higher consequence is chosen (with E= highest and A=lowest).

For example, in the event Out of Plane Bending Fatigue accumulated to the point it resulted in total failure and the loss of a Mooring Line, so the turbine must be run at a reduced capacity, the consequence of failure to the Mooring System would be Medium. If in the same event as the failure occurred, an employee was offshore carrying out O&M activities, as sustained a minor injury, the consequence in terms of health and safety would be Low, however as the higher ranking takes precedence the overall ranking would be Medium.

Table 8.2 Consequence of Failure Scoring and Criteria

	Consequence of Failure	Consequence to Mooring System	Health and Safety Consequence	Economic (£GBP)
A	Very Low	Mooring lines not lost, slightly degraded condition	Injury to employee requiring only minor first aid at most. Minimal health impact. No lost time.	1k
B	Low	Loss of mooring line or heavy degradation, turbine running at full capacity	Minor injury to an employee with full recovery. Short term health effects with full recovery and lost time.	10k
C	Medium	Lost a mooring line, turbine not shut down, but had to reduce loads and running at reduced capacity	More serious injury to an employee needing hospital treatment. Medium term health effects to an employee and lost time.	100k
D	High	Loss of mooring line resulting in turbine shut down.	Fatality or serious injury to a single employee. Off-site injuries needing treatment. Long term health effects or acute short term effects to a single	1m

			employee. Off-site health effects needing treatment.	
E	Very High	Whole mooring system shut down.	Multiple fatalities or serious injuries to employees and/or general public. Long term health effects or acute short term effects to employees or general public.	10m

8.3 Risk Matrix

Risk matrices are a useful means of graphically presenting the results from qualitative risk analyses. Risk matrices should, however, not be taken too literally since the scale of the axes is only indicative.

The risk matrix below has been proposed for the MooringSense project was developed and included within API 580 (1). This is currently seen as the ‘gold standard’ of risk-based inspection guidance and is applicable to multiple facility types (although it is to be noted it was not developed with offshore wind in mind) however the general concepts detailed within it can be applied as will be described within this section. This matrix draws attention to risks where the probability and consequence are balanced and to risks where either the probability or the consequence is high.

Risk is the product of the measure of the likelihood of occurrence of an undesired event and the potential adverse consequences which this event may have upon:

$$Risk = Likelihood \times Consequence$$

The matrix below is based on a linear scale of probability and consequence ranging from 1 to 5 and A to E. The numbers in the cells are the product of the probability and consequence values. This gives an overall risk rating.

Figure 8.1 Risk Matrix and Category Levels (1)

8.4 Risk Level and Inspection Frequency

Once a risk level has been quantified, this is then assigned to a correlated inspection frequency. Longer inspection intervals can be obtained based upon the calculated risk than those currently employed within time-based inspection methodologies. The key benefits of RBI are that the highest risk threats will be inspected more frequently and the associated inspections that are carried out are focussed to the areas which have a higher potential for failure. A blanket inspection approach based on a set inspection frequency will include areas within a system that have little chance of failing or causing production outages.

Table 8.3 shows the 4 risk levels, and the correlating inspection frequency assigned based on the risk.

Table 8.3 Risk Level and Correlated Inspection Frequency

Risk	Inspection Frequency
High	Once a year
Medium High	3 Years
Medium	5 years
Low	10 years

9. Risk Assessment

The inspection plan detailed in this section is followed once the initial baseline inspection (Detailed in Section 7) is complete and initial risk is determined.

If the baseline inspection highlights no areas of concern, then the below inspection plan should be implemented from a starting point of the date of baseline inspection. Any concerns found in the baseline inspection must be addressed before the plan is implemented, and a re-inspection of these areas is performed once the concerns are addressed. It is important to address issues found in the baseline inspection as soon as possible, as these will be in the warranty period for the manufacturer.

This is the initial inspection plan, which will be updated over time as information is gathered and risk levels may change according to this data.

9.1 Corrosion

Corrosion is capable of destroying the metallic structure of a chain and is one of the main causes of metal loss. The main forms of corrosion affecting chains are general corrosion, pitting corrosion, and microbiologically induced corrosion (MIC). Corrosion rates vary depending on water temperature, oxygenation, flow velocity and the presence of fouling or coral attacks in warmwater, among other factors. The corrosion rate can be obtained through the comparison of data collected from inspection, this is possible through measuring the remaining material thickness and the level of depleted cathodic protection.

9.1.1 Inspection Type

Detection of corrosion is primarily handled via close visual inspection (CVI); this is true for all forms expected. Non-Destructive Testing (NDT) methods such as ultra-sonic testing are available, however for a tailored inspection program the presence and location of the potential damage must be known.

9.1.2 Chain Catenary

Table 9.1 Chain Catenary Corrosion Risk Assessment

Segment	Risk	Inspection Frequency	Inspection Type
1	3A	Every 10 years	CVI via Diver/ROV*
2	3A	Every 10 years	CVI via Diver/ROV*
3	3A	Every 10 years	CVI via Diver/ROV*
4	4A	Every 5 years	CVI from landing*
5	4A	Every 5 years	CVI from landing*

**if damage is found, appropriate measurement will need to be taken and further investigated*

9.1.2.1 Risk Ranking Justification

Likelihood

Corrosion is a time-based mechanism so the risk at beginning of operation is lower. However, some forms of corrosion can be aggressive and quickly reduce the thickness of the chain, so risk is still medium at the beginning of operation. Accelerated corrosion is common in warmer waters due to MIC, so Likelihood classification may increase if this is identified in the location.

General corrosion can be found at any point on the chain surface along the mooring, however greater levels of corrosion are found in more oxygen rich water i.e., the splash zone (Oxygen exchange occurs primarily at the air-sea interface), so segment 4 and 5 have an increased Likelihood.

Consequence

At the beginning of operation, the consequence of corrosion is minimal as the mooring chains have a designed corrosion tolerance / allowance. As the years of operation increase and the thickness of the mooring chain link decreases, the consequence and risk level increases as the more likely the corrosion will result in complete failure.

Inspections may also find areas of accelerated corrosion, that will result in a change in risk, and this risk should be updated according to this data as part of the IM process.

9.1.3 Hybrid

Table 9.2 Hybrid Line Corrosion Risk Assessment

Segment	Risk	Inspection Frequency	Inspection Type
1-3	3A	Every 10 years	CVI via Diver/ROV*
4	0	n/a	n/a
5-7	3A	Every 10 years	CVI via Diver/ROV*
8,9	4A	Every 5 years	CVI from landing*

**if damage is found, appropriate measurement will need to be taken and further investigated*

9.1.3.1 Risk Ranking Justification

Likelihood

Corrosion is a time-based mechanism so risk at beginning of operation is lower. However, some forms of corrosion can be aggressive and quickly reduce the thickness of the chain, so risk is still medium at the beginning of operation. Accelerated corrosion is common in warmer waters due to MIC, so Likelihood classification may increase if this is identified in the location. General corrosion can be found at any point on the chain surface along the mooring, however greater levels of corrosion are found in more oxygen rich water i.e., the splash zone (Oxygen exchange occurs primarily at the air-sea interface), so segment 8 and 9 have an increased likelihood.

Segment 4, the synthetic section of the line, is not susceptible as this degradation effects exclusively chain mooring lines, and therefore is 0.

Consequence

At the beginning of operation, the consequence of corrosion is minimal as the mooring chains have a designed corrosion tolerance. As years of operation increase and the thickness of the mooring chain link decreases, the consequence and risk level increases as the more likely the corrosion will result in complete failure.

Inspections may also find areas of accelerated corrosion, that will result in a change in risk, and risk should be updated according to this data as part of the IM process.

9.2 Straight Tension Fatigue

With regards to steel mooring chains, the greatest form of damage is fatigue. Straight tension fatigue is the by-product of cyclic loading due to waves, wind and current affecting the floating platform and its mooring.

The repetitive nature of environmental loading allows for straight tension fatigue to accumulate over time (time dependant). For the most part, the bend section of chain links is most susceptible to incurring the highest levels of fatigue which can lead to failure of the chain link.

9.2.1 Inspection Type

Generally, straight tension fatigue is difficult to inspect for. There are some preferential areas for fatigue crack initiation, which can be inspected to indicate straight tension fatigue, via visual inspection and NDT techniques for crack can be carried out. There are also areas on the line that should be inspected more regularly based upon their likelihood to failure, such as the top chain link.

As it is difficult to inspect for straight tension fatigue, it is not worth the time and effort to inspect the whole line for cracks; instead, efforts should be targeted at the top segment of the line, where it is most likely to occur.

9.2.2 Chain Catenary

Table 9.3 Chain Catenary Straight Tension Fatigue Risk Assessment

Segment	Risk	Inspection Frequency	Inspection Type
1-4	4C	n/a	n/a
5	4C	Every 3 years	NDT - MPI or UT

9.2.2.1 Risk Ranking Justification

Likelihood

The repetitive nature of environmental loading allows for straight tension fatigue to accumulate over time (time dependent). The location of the straight tension fatigue phenomenon can be found along the complete mooring chain due to the effects of cyclic variation of axial loads.

Consequence

The accumulation of fatigue over time can result in fatigue crack propagation, and ultimately line failure.

9.2.3 Hybrid

Table 9.4 Hybrid Line Straight Tension Fatigue Risk Assessment

Segment	Risk	Inspection Frequency	Inspection Type
1-3	4C	n/a	n/a
4	0	n/a	n/a
5-8	4C	Every 3 years	n/a
9	4C	Every 3 years	NDT (MPI or UT)

9.2.3.1 Risk Ranking Justification

Likelihood

The repetitive nature of environmental loading allows for straight tension fatigue to accumulate over time (time dependent). The location of the straight tension fatigue phenomenon can be found along the complete mooring chain due to the effects of cyclic variation of axial loads.

Segment 4, the synthetic section of the line, is not susceptible as this degradation effects exclusively chain mooring lines, and therefore is 0.

Consequence

The accumulation of fatigue over time can result in fatigue crack propagation, and ultimately line failure.

9.3 Out of Plane Bending Fatigue

Out-of-plane-bending fatigue is the result of high axial loading, causing chain links to lock and behave in the same manner as a beam up until a certain bending moment threshold. Beyond which links begin to roll and slide against one another, this is a major contributor to fatigue crack propagation.

Out-of-plane-bending fatigue can typically be found between chain links at points of poor articulation, typically at the fairlead. For the most part, the bend section of chain links is most susceptible to incurring higher levels of fatigue. The inspection techniques that can be utilised for detection of out of plane bending fatigue are visual inspections and associated NDT techniques specifically techniques that look for crack detection

9.3.1 Inspection Type

Similar to straight tension fatigue, out of plane bending fatigue is difficult to inspect for. There are some preferential areas for fatigue crack initiation, which can be inspected to indicate out of plane bending fatigue, via visual inspection and NDT techniques for crack detection can be carried out. It particularly affects the first link after a link that is restrained, e.g. by a chain stopper in the floating structure so these can be targeted. It is unlikely to be of much benefit to do NDT for an entire line, as OPB fatigue is likely to be in specific areas only.

9.3.2 Chain Catenary

Table 9.5 Chain Catenary Out of Plane Bending Fatigue Risk Assessment

Segment	Risk	Inspection Frequency	Inspection Type
1	1C	n/a	n/a
2	1C	n/a	n/a
3	1C	n/a	n/a
4	1C	n/a	n/a
5	2C	Every 5 years	NDT (MPI or UT)

9.3.2.1 Risk Ranking Justification

Likelihood

In the SATH concept the upper chain segment is connected to the turret, partially above the mean seawater level, i.e., the splash zone. This section has the highest tension loads in the lines, as well as being subject to the largest rotations due to the relative motions between the platform and the moorings. Theoretically the risk of out of plane bending fatigue is high, however the SATH Platform has been designed using two connectors with pin-hole interfaces and low friction bushings, to accommodate the roll/pitch/yaw motions of the platform minimizing the transfer of bending moments to the first links, which reduces the risk.

Consequence

Out of Plane Bending stresses can be large enough to cause fatigue crack propagation and failure resulting in complete loss of a line, therefore the consequence of this failure mode is moderate.

9.3.3 Hybrid

Table 9.6 Hybrid Line Out of Plane Bending Fatigue Risk Assessment

Segment	Risk	Inspection Frequency	Inspection Type
1	1C	Every 5 years	Do not inspect
2	1C	Every 5 years	Do not inspect
3	2C	Every 5 years	Do not inspect
4	0	n/a	n/a
5	2C	Every 5 years	Do not inspect
6	1C	Every 5 years	Do not inspect
7	1C	Every 5 years	Do not inspect
8	1C	Every 5 years	Do not inspect

9	2C	Every 5 years	NDT (MPI or UT)
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9.3.3.1 Risk Ranking Justification

Likelihood

In the SATH concept the upper chain segment is connected to the turret, partially above the mean seawater level, i.e., the splash zone. This section has the highest tension loads in the lines, as well as being subject to the largest rotations due to the relative motions between the platform and the moorings. The risk of out of plane bending fatigue is high, although it is to be noted the SATH Platform has been designed using two connectors with pin-hole interfaces and low friction bushings, to accommodate the roll/pitch/yaw motions of the platform minimizing the transfer of bending moments to the first links, which somewhat mitigates the risk.

Segment 4, the synthetic section of the line, is not susceptible as this degradation effects exclusively chain mooring lines, and therefore is 0.

Consequence

Out of Plane Bending stresses can be large enough to cause fatigue crack propagation and failure resulting in complete loss of a line, therefore the consequence of this failure mode is moderate.

9.4 Wear

Wear between the chain links is commonly referred to interlink wear and is the result of adjoining links repeatedly being subject to relative motions. When tension is applied to the chain length, the inter-linked links come into contact with each other in an area termed the inter-grip area. Depending on the axial loads, and the amplitude of the rotation cycles between consecutive links the amount of interlink wear can vary. Excessive wear effects the chain's load handling capability.

9.4.1 Inspection Type

Detection of interlink wear is difficult, inspection will be with a diver or ROV to physically measure the cross sections at material contact interfaces.

9.4.2 Chain Catenary

Table 9.7 Chain Catenary Wear Risk Assessment

Segment	Risk	Inspection Frequency	Inspection Type
1-3	3A	Every 10 years	CVI via Diver/ROV*
4,5	4A	Every 5 years	CVI from landing*

**if damage is found, appropriate measurement will need to be taken and further investigated*

9.4.2.1 Risk Ranking Justification

Likelihood

The primary location to suffer wear is between the component interfaces. Largely found in the upper chain links but the mid catenary can also experience interlink wear to a degree, therefore Segments 4 and 5 are at an increased Likelihood.

Consequence

At the beginning of operation, the consequence of wear is minimal as the mooring chains are designed with a tolerance to wear. As years of operation increase and the thickness of the mooring chain link decreases, the consequence and risk level increases as the more likely the wear will result in complete failure.

9.4.3 Hybrid

Table 9.8 Hybrid Line Wear Risk Assessment

Segment	Risk	Inspection Frequency	Inspection Type
1	2A	Every 10 years	CVI via Diver/ROV*
2	2A	Every 10 years	CVI via Diver/ROV*
3	2A	Every 10 years	CVI via Diver/ROV*
4	0	n/a	CVI via Diver/ROV*
5	2A	Every 10 years	CVI via Diver/ROV*
6	4A	Every 5 years	CVI via Diver/ROV*
7	4A	Every 5 years	CVI via Diver/ROV*
8	4A	Every 5 years	CVI from landing*
9	4A	Every 5 years	CVI from landing*

**if damage is found, appropriate measurement will need to be taken and further investigated*

9.4.3.1 Risk Ranking Justification

Likelihood

The primary location to suffer wear is between component interfaces. Largely found in the upper chain links but mid catenary can also experience interlink wear to a degree, therefore Segments 6 to 9 are at an increased Likelihood.

Segment 4, the synthetic section of the line, is not susceptible as this degradation effects exclusively chain mooring lines, and therefore is 0.

Consequence

At the beginning of operation, the consequence of wear is minimal as the mooring chains are designed with a tolerance to wear. As years of operation increase and the thickness of the mooring chain link

decreases, the consequence and risk level increases as the more likely the wear will result in complete failure.

9.5 Mechanical Damage

Chains can be subjected to mechanical damage during transport, installation or while in service. Typical mechanical damages can occur due to due to impacts with other metallic parts such as: vessel interaction, anchor drag, ROV impact etc.

*Please note Mechanical Damage refers to only the metallic parts of the structure. Damage to the synthetic section is covered in Section 9.7.

9.5.1 Inspection Type

Mechanical damage is primary inspected by visual inspection, with a diver or ROV.

9.5.2 Chain Catenary

This degradation mechanism is only applicable to the hybrid mooring line solution.

Table 9.9 Chain Catenary Mechanical Damage Risk Assessment

Segment	Risk	Inspection Frequency	Inspection Type
1-3	2C	Every 5 years	CVI via Diver/ROV*
4,5	2C	Every 5 years	CVI from landing*

9.5.2.1 Risk Ranking Justification

Likelihood

Damage of this nature could occur at any location; thus, Likelihood is uniform along the chain. The risk is generally low; however, it can increase with an increased presence of boats in and around the windfarm.

The Likelihood is much higher during the transport and installation, however any defects due to this will be observed within the baseline inspection, therefore the risk remains low. Likelihood may increase throughout the lifetime of the windfarm, as inspection frequency is likely to increase and more frequent inspections increases the chance of ROV impact), fishing/trawling activity

Consequence

Mechanical damage can vary in terms of the damage caused, however it can in turn increase the risk of other damage mechanisms. The risk from mechanical damage may increase over time as the chain thickness decreases due to wear and corrosion, and the chain can withstand less force.

9.5.3 Hybrid

Table 9.10 Hybrid Line Mechanical Damage Risk Assessment

Segment	Risk	Inspection Frequency	Inspection Type
1-3	2C	Every 5 years	CVI via Diver/ROV*
4	0	n/a	n/a
5-7	2C	Every 5 years	CVI via Diver/ROV*
8,9	2C	Every 5 years	CVI from landing*

9.5.3.1 Risk Ranking Justification

Likelihood

Damage of this nature could occur at any location; thus, Likelihood is uniform along the chain. The risk is generally low, however can increase with increased presence of boats in and around the windfarm.

Likelihood is much higher during transport and installation; however, this will be accounted for in the baseline inspection, so risk remains low. Likelihood may increase throughout the lifetime of the windfarm, as inspection frequency is likely to increase and more frequent inspections increases the chance of ROV impact), fishing/trawling activity

Segment 4, the synthetic section of the line, is not susceptible as this degradation effects exclusively chain mooring lines, and therefore is 0.

Consequence

Mechanical damage can vary in terms of the damage caused, however can in turn increase the risk of other damage mechanisms. The risk from mechanical damage may increase over time as the chain thickness decreases due to wear and corrosion, and the chain can withstand less force.

9.6 Tension fatigue

Tension fatigue occurs in steel wire or synthetic ropes subjected to fluctuating loads over an extended period of repeated cycles during use. It results in degradation of the material and a reduction in the strength of the rope. The impact of repeated tension cycles on the rope's strength is typically a function of the stress level exerted on the rope, as well as the material and construction characteristics of the rope. Ropes tend to have an extended fatigue life due to the high number of discrete components acting in parallel. If local imperfections lead to premature failure of a single components in a rope (e.g., a filament or wire) the load at the failure locations can be re-distributed amongst the remaining components with negligible effect and the helical structure of ropes will enable the load to be transferred back into the damaged component either side of the failure location. In this way, damage can be isolated and will not propagate across the rope.

9.6.1 Inspection Type

Tension fatigue is difficult to inspect for. There may be evidence of failure of single components in a rope that can be seen by visual inspection, however unless they are located on the outside of the rope this will be hard to see. The mooring sense synthetic rope will also have an outer sheath that will make it not possible to see any failures unless this results in a break in the outer sheath also.

9.6.2 Chain Catenary

This degradation mechanism is only applicable to the hybrid mooring line solution.

9.6.3 Hybrid

Table 9.11 Hybrid Line Tension Fatigue Risk Assessment

Segment	Risk	Inspection Frequency	Inspection Type
1-3	0	n/a	n/a
4	2A	Every 10 years	Do not Inspect
6-9	0	n/a	n/a

9.6.3.1 Risk Ranking Justification

Likelihood

In conventional mooring systems, fatigue life of ropes is normally greater than that of chain. Consequently, the chain in the system normally becomes the fatigue limiting component and little emphasis is placed on rope fatigue. In the reference case, the synthetic segment of the mooring line is also not an area that is known to be susceptible to high levels of fatigue, so Likelihood in this case is low. This is a synthetic rope degradation mechanism only and therefore only will affect Segment 4.

Consequence

If tension fatigue accumulates, as discussed, the load at the failure locations can be re-distributed amongst the remaining components with negligible effect. Fatigue is a time dependent mechanism so this may change throughout operation, however, is unlikely to ever result in failure, as the chain segments would fail first, so consequence and overall risk remains low.

9.7 External damage (abrasion, cutting and wear)

External damage is the most common cause of significant degradation (i.e., requiring repair or replacement) in mooring ropes, and can be caused by abrasion, cutting, and crushing. This may be through contact with other mooring system components (particularly chains), contact with sub-sea operations equipment (e.g., ROVs or work wires), contact with fishing gear and contact with installation equipment.

External damage can be categorised in three divisions: (i) complete destruction of the load bearing part of the rope (the core), (ii) partial destruction of the load bearing part of the rope and (iii) damage to the non-load bearing outer parts of the rope.

The overall effect on fatigue life will depend on the magnitude of the damage sustained.

9.7.1 Inspection Type

Detection of external damage is primarily handled via visual inspection; by diver or ROV.

9.7.2 Chain Catenary

This degradation mechanism is only applicable to the hybrid mooring line solution.

9.7.3 Hybrid

Table 9.12 Hybrid Line External Damage Risk Assessment

Segment	Risk	Inspection Frequency	Inspection Type
1-3	0	n/a	n/a
4	2D	Every 5 years	CVI
5-9	0	n/a	n/a

9.7.3.1 Risk Ranking Justification

Likelihood

External damages are a likely to arise during installation, which can only be detected by performing visual inspections of the mooring lines during installation or during maintenance periods, however this should be covered in the baseline inspection. As this degradation is mostly governed by external factors e.g., probability of a collision to occur, Likelihood will be linked to external activity in the specific area. Likelihood will increase alongside frequency of inspections due to the increase in ROVs/boats etc that cause this damage. This is a synthetic rope degradation mechanism only and therefore only will affect Segment 4.

Consequence

Consequence depends largely on the magnitude of the damage caused. However, as this damage is likely to occur when personnel are in the area, the consequence is high.

9.8 UV radiation

UV radiation is not normally considered a significant risk to mooring ropes in its own right (i.e., the risk of degradation to the mechanical properties of ropes is low). However, UV radiation accelerates marine growth which in turn can lead to other degradation mechanisms. To date, there has been relatively little research into marine growth on mooring ropes since chain is often the preferred material in the upper 100m of the mooring line with consequently minimal growth on mooring ropes.

9.8.1 Inspection Type

You are unable to inspect directly for UV. Excessive marine growth can be inspected for by visual inspection, which may indicate high levels of UV, however UV itself cannot be inspected for.

9.8.2 Chain Catenary

This degradation mechanism is only applicable to the hybrid mooring line solution.

9.8.3 Hybrid

Table 9.13 Hybrid Line UV Radiation Risk Assessment

Segment	Risk	Inspection Frequency	Inspection Type
1-3	0	n/a	n/a
4	1A	Every 10 years	Do not Inspect
5-9	0	n/a	n/a

9.8.3.1 Risk Ranking Justification

Likelihood

The synthetic segment of the system is at lower water depths and therefore unlikely to be exposed to high levels of UV.

Consequence

Consequence is low as the UV does not pose much risk in terms of degradation to the mechanical properties of the rope. Any degradation from other mechanisms which the UV accelerates, will be accounted for in other sections of the risk assessment.

9.9 Marine growth

Marine growth is typically a concern for the upper 100m of mooring line, given the SATH concept, this likely to spread onto the synthetic portion of the line. Although the effects of marine fouling are not critical in terms of an increase in risk, a more time dependant approach is required to understand the effect such as an accumulation of growth (added mass) and its effects on the catenary. The full length is susceptible to fouling however the top section is more likely to experience this due to the availability of UV radiation. Added mass through marine growth may cause contact between the seabed and synthetic portion of a mooring line, which can lead to particle ingress or damage to the outer sheath.

9.9.1 Inspection Type

Inspection for Marine Growth is done via visual inspection, either by a diver or ROV.

9.9.2 Chain Catenary

This degradation mechanism is only applicable to the hybrid mooring line solution.

9.9.3 Hybrid

Table 9.14 Hybrid Line Marine Growth Risk Assessment

Segment	Risk	Inspection Frequency	Inspection Type
1-3	0	n/a	n/a
4	3B	Every 10 years	GVI
5-9	0	n/a	n/a

9.9.3.1 Risk Ranking Justification

Likelihood

This is a synthetic rope degradation mechanism only and therefore only will affect Segment 4.

Consequence

Marine growth is a time dependent mechanism and therefore risk increases throughout operation, however initially the consequence is low, as small amounts of added mass are unlikely to have an effect on the line. Additionally, marine growth is required to be removed if/when an inspection is required, therefore after each inspection the consequence should be re-evaluated.

This threat may be detected by the Structural Health Monitoring System and data from this may be used to inform the risk ranking whilst in operation, and consequently be revised. This is discussed in detail in Section 15.5.

9.10 Elongation and Axial Stiffness Change

All ropes will undergo some degree of permanent elongation when first loaded. For steel ropes this is not normally considered significant. However, for fibre ropes this elongation can influence mooring system integrity. For example, as a rope length increases the risk of seabed contact may increase, tensions may reduce and wear and fatigue modes (of both the rope and the system) may change. This characteristic may be particularly relevant in FOWT mooring systems which, unlike oil and gas mooring systems, will have limited opportunity to re-tension lines. Due to both rope construction and material properties the axial stiffness of synthetic fibre ropes changes as a function of mean load, load range, cycle frequency and, most significantly, load history. Consequently, the axial stiffness properties cannot be taken as a constant and will evolve with the operation of the system.

9.10.1 Inspection Type

Axial stiffness cannot be inspected for currently. Elongation is also difficult to inspect for, it is difficult to measure an entire line.

9.10.2 Chain Catenary

This degradation mechanism is only applicable to the hybrid mooring line solution.

9.10.3 Hybrid

Table 9.15 Hybrid Line Elongation and Axial Stiffness Change Risk Assessment

Segment	Risk	Inspection Frequency	Inspection Type
1-3	0	n/a	n/a
4	3A	Every 10 years	Do not inspect
5-9	0	n/a	n/a

9.10.3.1 Risk Ranking Justification

Likelihood

Excessive elongation after initial hook up should be detected in the baseline inspection. Beyond this Likelihood is fairly low but may increase when the line is subjected to excessive loads, such as in a storm. Axial stiffness properties may also be affected by this. This is a synthetic rope degradation mechanism only and therefore only will affect Segment 4.

Consequence

Elongation itself will not cause failure of the line but will increase Likelihood to other mechanisms such as seabed contact and particle ingress.

This threat may be detected by the Structural Health Monitoring System and data from this may be used to inform the risk ranking whilst in operation, and consequently be revised. This is discussed in detail in Section 15.5.

9.11 Seabed Contact and Particle Ingress

Seabed contact is not normally recommended for mooring ropes in operation as it may lead to wear or abrasion and particle ingress. However, it can be acceptable for ropes to occasionally touch the seabed during operation (e.g., leeward lines in extreme weather). The permeable nature of synthetic fibre ropes means that small particles (e.g., clay, silt, or sand) can enter the rope and act as an abrasive medium. Ropes which are temporarily laid on the seabed or touch the seabed during operation are particularly at risk. Particles entering the load bearing core can accelerate wear in tension fatigue and can significantly influence the splice area.

9.11.1 Inspection Type

Seabed contact can be seen by general visual inspection with diver or ROV. Particle ingress itself is inspectable

9.11.2 Chain Catenary

This degradation mechanism is only applicable to the hybrid mooring line solution.

9.11.3 Hybrid

Table 9.16 Hybrid Line Seabed Contact and Particle Ingress Risk Assessment

Segment	Risk	Inspection Frequency	Inspection Type
1-3	0	n/a	n/a
4	2A	Every 10 years	GVI
5-9	0	n/a	n/a

9.11.3.1 Risk Ranking Justification

Likelihood

Damage through seabed contact is most likely to occur in the lower portions of hybrid mooring lines. Only the synthetic section is susceptible as this phenomenon only affects synthetic mooring lines.

The hybrid solution has buoyancy modules distributed along the rope to avoid seabed contact once installation has occurred, so risk should be low, and only occur if significant elongation of the entire rope/chain occurs that makes it drag along the seabed.

Mooring ropes are commonly stored on the seabed prior to mooring system hook up where they can be exposed to these threats. Although more obvious signs of abrasion or wear from the seabed may be seen in the baseline inspection, particle ingress may be difficult to see in inspection, unless it has already caused notable damage.

Excessive elongation in the rope can make the mooring line more susceptible. If elongation is detected, the Likelihood to seabed contact and particle ingress will increase.

Consequence

The impact from particle ingress is time dependent and will develop with the operational use of the mooring line. As years of operation increase the consequence and risk level may increase as the more likely the particle ingress will result in a reduction in load bearing capabilities of the rope.

10. Risk Assessment Results - Summary

Table 10.1 and Table 10.2 below display a summary of the risk ranking for each type of Mooring Line, per segment.

10.1 Chain Catenary

Table 10.1 Chain Catenary Risk Assessment Results Summary

Segment	Corrosion (including general, MIC, Pitting)	Straight Tension Fatigue	Out of Plane Bending Fatigue	Wear	Mechanical Damage
1	3A	4C	1C	3A	2C
2	3A	4C	1C	3A	2C
3	3A	4C	1C	3A	2C
4	4A	4C	1C	4A	2C
5	4A	4C	2C	4A	2C

10.2 Hybrid

Table 10.2 Hybrid Risk Assessment Results Summary

Segment	Chain Degradation Mechanisms					Synthetic Degradation Mechanisms					
	Corrosion (including general, MIC, Pitting)	Straight Tension Fatigue	Out of Plane Bending Fatigue	Wear	Mechanical Damage	Tension fatigue	External damage (abrasion, cutting and wear)	UV radiation	Marine growth	Elongation and Axial Stiffness	Seabed contact and particle ingress
1	3A	4C	1C	2A	2C	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	3A	4C	1C	4A	2C	0	0	0	0	0	0
3	3A	4C	2C	2A	2C	0	0	0	0	0	0
4	0	0	0	0	0	2A	2D	1A	3B	3A	2A
5	3A	4C	2C	2A	2C	0	0	0	0	0	0
6	4A	4C	1C	4A	2C	0	0	0	0	0	0
7	4A	4C	1C	4A	2C	0	0	0	0	0	0
8	4A	4C	1C	4A	2C	0	0	0	0	0	0
9	4A	4C	2C	4A	2C	0	0	0	0	0	0

11. Inspection Plan

After the Risk Assessment has been performed and risk levels identified, the inspection programme is developed to reduce the risk.

An effective inspection plan establishes:

1. What type of damage to look for?
2. Where to look for damage.
3. How to look for damage.
4. When to look for damage.

The inspection plan targets those areas of highest risk as determined by the risk assessment, by inspecting them more frequently, as determined by the inspection intervals in Table 8.3. The inspection plan is followed only once the initial baseline inspection (Detailed in Section 7) is complete and initial risk is determined. The inspection frequency in the plan below has been dictated by the highest risk segment for that degradation mechanism, and is a summary of the risk and inspection.

11.1 Chain Catenary Baseline Inspection Plan

Table 11.1 Chain Catenary Inspection Plan

What inspecting for	How	Where	Frequency – Driven by highest risk segment
Corrosion	Close Visual Inspection	Whole Chain	Every 5 years
Straight Tension Fatigue	Close Visual inspection and NDT for cracks (MPI or UT)	Segment 5 only	Every 3 years
OPB Fatigue	Close Visual inspection and NDT for cracks	Segment 5 only	Every 5 years
Wear	Close Visual Inspection	Whole Chain	Every 5 years
Mechanical Damage	General Visual Inspection	Whole Chain	Every 5 years

11.2 Hybrid Solution Baseline Inspection Plan

Table 11.2 Hybrid Solution Baseline Inspection Plan

What inspecting for	How	Where	Frequency
Corrosion	Close Visual Inspection	Whole line (except synthetic segment 5)	Every 5 years
Straight Tension Fatigue	Close Visual inspection and NDT for cracks (MPI or UT)	Segment 9 only	Every 3 years
OPB Fatigue	Close Visual inspection and NDT for cracks (MPI or UT)	Segment 9 only	Every 3 years
Wear	Close Visual Inspection	Whole line (except synthetic segment 5)	Every 5 years
Mechanical Damage	General Visual Inspection	Whole line	Every 5 years
Tension Fatigue	Do not inspect	Segment 5	n/a
External Damage	Close Visual inspection	Segment 5	Every 5 years
UV Radiation	Do not inspect	Segment 5	n/a
Marine Growth	General Visual Inspection	Segment 5	Every 10 years
Elongation and Axial Stiffness Change	Do not inspect	Segment 5	n/a
Seabed contact and particle ingress	General Visual Inspection	Whole line but focusing on Segments 1-5	Every 10 years

11.3 Optimising Inspection Frequency

Offshore operations are generally very costly and require specialised personnel and equipment.

Generally, to perform a subsea visual inspection of mooring lines the following is required:

- ROV support vessel (and related vessel crew in shifts)
- Inspection class ROV fitted with camera and video
- ROV crew (2-3 persons for 12hr shift)

Therefore if 2 segments are scheduled to be inspected within a small timeframe, it is usually best practice to combine the inspections, to optimise OPEX. It is difficult to estimate cost of inspection, however average day rates are given below in Table 11.3 based on industry experience:

Table 11.3 Visual Inspection Costs

	Average day rates [€/day]
Support Vessel	10,000 – 30,000
Inspection class ROV	3,000-5,000
ROV crew (*)	1,000
Other inspection equipment (**)	1,000-10,000

(*) cost per person. Generally, 4-6 people required for 24hr operation

(**) depends on the type of inspection

Considering, for example the average of the prices in Table 11.3, for 7-day operation for a visual inspection we have a total daily cost of 30,000EUR and a total cost for 7 days of 210,000 EUR

In order to effectively optimise cost and inspection frequency, generally inspections will be driven by the highest risk segment for each degradation mechanism. If 2 separate scheduled inspections are within 2 years of each other, it should be assessed whether or not it may be suitable to combine them, particularly if the overall risk is low.

12. External Event Based Inspections

External Event based inspections are those which are driven by an event which is thought to have the potential to cause significant damage or degradation.

These are events resulting from

- Forces of nature
- Acts of sabotage
- Neighbouring fires or explosions
- Neighbouring hazardous material releases
- Electrical power failures
- Tornadoes
- Earthquakes
- Intrusions of external transportation vehicles, such as aircraft, ships, trains, trucks, or automobiles.

External events are usually beyond the direct or indirect control of persons employed at or by the facility.

Typically, operators should have access to geological and weather data that will inform them of a storm or other extreme weather in the area. Additionally, data from the smart sensors can flag unusual positions or orientations of the sensor may be attributed to bad weather or other unforeseen events and can indicate the need for an ad-hoc inspection. As data is gathered from the sensors, unusual movements/positioning data will become clearer to operators and what will indicate a storm or severe damage. The structural health monitoring system may also indicate an 'unhealthy' state if the extreme even has caused damage to the mooring lines to the extent that it affects the platform movement. All of these can be used in combination to indicate an inspection is required.

13. Risk Re-Assessment Following Examination

The initial RBI plans from the design phase are only a starting point. As inspections and in-service data are collected, these plans should be revised based on their results. RBI teams should meet after inspections and data collection and reassess the risk of failure. If any modifications are made, such as repairs or changes to operation, these should also be considered.

Particularly, RBI teams should assess whether actions taken as a result of previous expectations have had the intended effect. The condition of the Mooring line may be better, or worse, or the same as was estimated from the risk assessment. If it is as expected, and any actions taken have had the intended effect, the risk assessment process will have been effective. If condition differs significantly from what was estimated, either much better or worse, then the risk should be re-assessed. Previous actions may need to be reviewed and modified accordingly.

Possible outcomes of re-assessment are:

- The assumptions made were reasonably conservative, so no adjustments to the initial risk assessment are necessary.
- The assumptions were not sufficiently conservative or a new, or unanticipated, deterioration mechanism is identified.
- The assumptions were significantly over conservative, and the evidence suggests a re-assessment would give a lower risk ranking in the next assessment. In this event, the risk should be re-assessed.
- A combination of the above.

The RBI team will need to consider if the assessment carried out was appropriate after assessing the data and results. Unanticipated deterioration may require the use of different NDT and/or widening the inspection scope in the re-assessment. The new knowledge may also indicate similar areas of the windfarm also need to be re-assessed, due to experiencing similar conditions that may increase the likelihood of certain deterioration mechanisms.

It should also be noted that inspection, repair and change to operational environment can also reduce the risk ranking for areas of the mooring line. This means the inspection programme can be revised to focus on higher risk areas, and inspections for these areas reduced.

The entirety of the risk assessment process is dependent on the quantity and quality of data available for the windfarm at the time of assessment, and the knowledge and experience of the RBI team conducting it. The assessment will only reflect the situation at the time the data was collected. Therefore, if the basis of the risk assessment changes, a whole re-assessment must be carried out with the most recent information available. The risk ranking process is dynamic and will change with operating history and the results of inspection. Although previous assessments may reflect good engineering judgement and experience, it is always necessary to review and re-validate the assumptions using the most recent information available.

Prior to inspection, it is usually considered best practice to re-assess the risk to evaluate whether the basis of the previous risk assessment remains valid. Re-assessment should also be carried out at times during service if key data used in the risk assessment changes or as a result of events or changes in circumstances. It is therefore important to keep in communication with the RBI team and the operators

whilst the windfarm is in operation in the event any operational modifications are made. Things that may justify a re-assessment of risk include

- A serious operational upset.
- Failure of an item of equipment.
- Change in the operational regime.
- Change in the internal or external operating environment.
- Where time dependant operating conditions exist such as fatigue or creep.
- Change in industry practice.
- Change in windfarm management or ownership.
- Change in the level of operator training and knowledge.

Over time, the risk profile across the farm itself will change and some turbines will be higher risk than others. Differences in where they are positioned across the wind farm may make them more prone to certain degradation mechanisms. Over time operators will gain a clearer understanding of risks in the facility and higher risk turbines. Priority turbines and lines can be identified for inspection, and inspections of lower risk lines can be pushed out.

14. Mitigation, Intervention and Repair

When a mooring line failure or serious degradation is found, a response plan should be followed that have been pre-emptively developed for a range of possible failure scenarios. Effective implementation of response plans can reduce the impact of failures and limit the severity of the operational impact to the windfarm/turbine.

Effective pre-emptive response planning involves:

- Identifying possible failure and degradation scenarios
- How the failures/ degradation will be detected
- Initial response procedures
- Long term mitigation and improvement plans

14.1 Short-term response

The short-term emergency plans should consider:

- The personnel included in the plan, their organisation, and responsibilities, and how they will communicate. This may include (but not limited to) inspection personnel, offshore facility personnel, operators, and regulators.
- Site shutdown and evacuation procedures
- Production shutdown and evacuation requirements.
- Mooring line disconnection procedures and weather limits.
- Emergency mooring line re-connection procedures, and where to find spare parts and vessels
- Assessment of emergency towing equipment, safe havens, and towing procedures.

14.2 Long-term response

Long term procedures following a response should be implemented to avoid future failure. A root cause analysis should be performed to identify the causes of failures and degradation, and to define appropriate modifications to the design and operation of the windfarm. If the failed component is repaired and reinstated into the windfarm, the results from the root cause analysis should be taken into account.

15. Utilising the MooringSense Concept

The Mooring Sense project involves the development and use of a set of technological enablers that have been developed within the project. This includes development of a low-cost smart sensor for FOWT motion monitoring, a Mooring System Digital Twin (DT) model, Structural Health Monitoring (SHM) techniques, as well as control strategies for mooring condition management tolerance at turbine and farm levels. Full descriptions of these tools can be found in Deliverables D2.4 (RD-01), D3.4 (RD-05), and D5.1 (RD-06) and D6.3 (RD-07).

A summary of the MooringSense tools can be seen in Table 15.1 below.

Table 15.1 MooringSense Tools Description

Tool	Function	Output
Tool 1: Virtual measurement of mooring line loads	To numerically identify the mooring line loads from the motions measured by the Smart Sensor.	Main output will be the mooring line axial tensions, and the inline and out of plane bending moments in the case of chain segments.
Tool 2: Continuous calculation of synthetic rope properties	To calculate the elongation, the static and the dynamic stiffnesses based on the actual mooring line load history.	The method should be able to adequately determine installation length / change in length (elongation), dynamic stiffness, static stiffness, extreme force, and extreme length.
Tool 3: Prediction of floater motions	To predict the floater motions based on environmental data from sensors, or from forecasts.	The outputs from the simulations are time histories of the floater motions. The simulation tool will provide, in addition to the floater motions, many other responses of the system such as: mooring system loads and dynamics, hydrodynamic loads on the floater, structural responses of the turbine, servo loads, etc. These are not relevant for the present sub-section.

Tool 4: Calculation of remaining lifetime	To calculate the remaining fatigue lifetime based on the fatigue damage induced by the actual mooring line loads.	The output of this tool will be both the RUL of undamaged chains and the RUL of synthetic ropes with damages. Those predictions will be used by the SHM system as an additional source of information, since certain damages are more likely to occur at the end of component's life showing a remarkable correlation with RUL.
Tool 5: Mooring re-analysis	To update the safety factors based on updated system or environmental information.	The results are the ULS, ALS and FLS safety factors, together with relevant detailed information such as predicted maximum loads, critical load cases, etc.
Tool 6: Calculation of local damages in chains	To calculate local damages in chains using the actual mooring line loads history.	The tool will estimate the RUL (in years) for a crack to grow to its critical size. This will be performed for one link in each mooring line. To this respect the most conservative situation will be studied: a link in the splash zone (whose corrosion ratio is the highest in the line).

MooringSense therefore provides a wealth of information that can inform the risk assessment process. These tools can be leveraged to provide information about the integrity of the mooring lines without the expense of going offshore. The risk assessment cycle (as seen in Figure 2.1) always starts with 'Data and Information and Gathering', and the Digital Twin provides a unique opportunity to support the traditional information that would be gathered as part of this step.

The data paints a picture of the state and condition of the system, to aid in the prediction and/or detection of damage before it reaches levels critical to safe operation. The aim is to use what available data there is to make the most informed decision regarding the integrity and longevity of the mooring lines. This allows for predictive maintenance as well as low risk operation. Data usually falls into either characteristic or condition data, both of which can be useful in informing the IM process.

Some of the MooringSense SHM system and digital twin tools require historical operational data to identify specific failure scenarios and degradation mechanisms, that cannot be obtained until in use on an operational windfarm. The tools/SHM therefore in lieu of inspections, and instead are used as additional support to the traditional methods of data gathering (e.g., inspections and historical failure data).

The tools will therefore be used to adjust the inspection plan presented in Section 11, according to a series of parameters that will be decided on the data the tools output. The tools will enhance the decision-making processes for inspection and maintenance operation.

In the future as data is gathered and the tools are able to classify more damages and degradation through historical data, at more sensitive tolerances, it is envisioned the strategy will develop to place more of a reliance on the digital twin data. At present, the tools are unable to identify in a lot of cases the exact cause of degraded condition, and thus traditional inspections must still be performed.

15.1 Tool 1 - Virtual measurement of mooring line loads.

Tool 1 will provide a "virtual measurement" of the mooring line axial tensions. Virtual measurement means the loads are not measured themselves but provided in real time and calculated from measured motions, using a finite element model of the mooring line, using the fairlead forcing motions as the input. For mooring lines with a chain segment starting at the fairlead, the tool will also provide inline and out of plane bending moments at the first link due to friction effects. The input platform motions are measured by the Smart Sensor (RD-03).

Tool 1 can be used as part of the IM strategy to inform operators which mooring lines are being exposed to the highest loads, and therefore may be at a greater risk of failure. In terms of inspection, these lines can be prioritised. Inspections for those lines which are being exposed to minimal loads can be considered for delaying inspection, in order to optimise resources and save on costs.

15.2 Tool 2 – Continuous calculation of synthetic rope properties

Tool 2 continuously calculates the elongation, the static and dynamic stiffness based on the actual mooring line load history. This can be achieved by acquiring virtual line loads from Tool 1, which are used as a basis input in a numerical model for calculating parameters such as axial stiffness and elongation (RD-03). The effects from marine fouling and seabed contact are directly monitored within the DT by monitoring the stiffness/elongation of the mooring lines.

If the Tool detects significant elongation or changes in static or dynamic stiffness, the operator should consider an inspection, replacement, or plan for mitigation (e.g., re-tensioning the lines), based on the severity of the degradation. It is up to operators to decide at what point the changes in these properties become unacceptable and will trigger an immediate plan for inspection or replacement. This will depend on the line used (a certain degree of permanent elongation is typically expected when the lines are first loaded and this is factored into the design), and this will also change depending on how many years into operation the mooring line is, as some changes in these properties can be expected across the operational lifespan.

15.3 Tool 4 - Calculation of remaining lifetime.

Tool 4 calculates the remaining life of the mooring chain is calculated through two different methods:

- i) Transfer function
- ii) Model base on ROM.

The purpose of transfer functions is to provide relationships between loads and stresses at critical spots. These functions are based on stress concentration factors, described in Deliverable 3.3 Numerical modelling – degradation and failure, which are developed by means of local finite element models. ROMs are built using the Von Mises stresses computed through FEA for different snapshots. Afterwards, stresses are estimated applying machine learning algorithms, such as Gauss Process Regression. Finally, Rainflow Counting algorithm and Miner’s law are applied to estimate the cumulative damage and RUL in either approaches, while considering the effects of corrosion by applying the correspondent SN curves and stress concentration factors. While different in nature, both approaches have revealed to be consistent for the purpose of assessing the cumulated damage and remnant life, which validates the Project Tool developed.

A full description of the Tool’s architecture can be found in Deliverable 3.4.

15.3.1 Use of Tool 4 in the Integrity Management Strategy

As discussed above, Tool 4 will provide a Remaining Useful Life value in years. This should be divided by the Years of Design Life left for the facility, and the inspection frequencies for **Straight Tension Fatigue** and **Out of Plane Bending Fatigue** are altered by the amount displayed in Table 15.2 below.

$$x = \frac{\text{Remaining Useful Life}}{\text{Years of Operation Left}}$$

Table 15.2 Remaining Useful Life and Effect on Inspection Frequency

Remaining Useful Life / Years left of Operation	Effect on Inspection Frequency
$x \geq 2$	Evaluate delaying inspection by 3-5 years
$2 > x \geq 1.5$	Evaluate delaying inspection by 1-2 years
$1.5 > x \geq 1$	Baseline Inspection Plan
$1 > x \geq 0.5$	Investigate cause Plan for inspection
≤ 0.5	Immediate inspection

For example, if the remaining useful life is 40years, and the years left of operation is 15, the remaining useful life is 2.67 times the years left of operation. Using Table 15.2, this is greater than 2, and therefore the RBI team/operator should consider delaying inspection by 3 to 5 years.

If for example the remaining useful life is 10 years and there is 20 years left of operation this is 0.5 and using Table 15.2, an immediate inspection should be carried out.

15.4 Tool 6 - Calculation of local damages in chains

Tool 6 calculates the consequence of local damage in chain links. The tool will consist of one module and which will deal with cracks and will firstly assess a relationship between Stress Intensity Factor (SIF), loads and cracks for the damaged links. The SIF will then be used to establish the maximum allowable crack by means of a Failure Assessment Diagram (FAD). The tool will calculate the crack

growth from an initial crack with the real load histogram and a proper Paris law. The final crack after 5 years can be obtained, and the result compared to the maximum allowable crack from the FAD.

The tool will output a RUL for cracks in years. For this the following equation should be used.

$$x = \frac{\text{Length of Crack after 5 years}}{\text{Length of crack at failure}}$$

Table 15.3 Remaining Useful Life of Crack and Effect on Inspection Frequency

Length of Crack after 5 years/Length of crack at failure	Effect on Inspection Frequency
$x < 0.5$	Baseline Inspection Plan
$0.5 > x \geq 0.75$	Inspection in next year
$0.75 > x \geq 1$	Immediate inspection and plan for replacement/repair

The value should then be assessed using Table 15.3. Cracks which are close in length to the length of the crack at failure will require immediate inspection, or an inspection in the next year, depending on severity. Cracks identified that are not at immediate risk of failure should be closely monitored and will need to be considered in risk re-assessment for that segment of the mooring chain.

15.5 Structural Health Monitoring System

The Structural Health Monitoring (SHM) System is a data driven, continuous (online) monitoring system that considers a global scope (i.e., the entire structure), oriented to assess the health of the mooring lines of the FOWTs in a wind farm. It goes through 4 steps:

- 1) Operational Evaluation
- 2) Data Acquisition and Cleansing
- 3) Feature Extraction and Data Compression
- 4) Statistical Model Development for Feature Discrimination(diagnosis)

In the MooringSense concept, the purpose of the SHM system is to detect and classify damages in the mooring system at early stages, by fusing environmental and positioning data coming from different sources and reporting the health condition of the moorings.

The SHM system detects damage by recognising that the platform is moving in a different way compared to similar environmental and operational conditions in the past when it supposedly was healthy or undamaged. This is what is known as a semi-supervised situation, that is, the system knows when the mooring system was healthy. The new data is compared to the data from that healthy period and detects any changes that may indicate a fault in the mooring line. A full description of how the system works can be seen in Deliverable 2.4 (RD-03) and Deliverable 5.1 (RD-07).

The damages that are being considered in the analysis and validation of the SHM in WP5 are shown in Table 15.4. In task T5.4, the ability of the SHM to detect and classify those damages is being validated

Table 15.4 Damages Detectable by the SHM System

Damaged situation	
1	Loss of mooring line
2	Anchor drag
3	Buoyancy damage
4	Clump weight release
5	Fibre rope degradation (max 3% elongation)
6	Chain degradation
7	Slacked line
8	Marine growth, fouling
9	Trawler snag
10	Platform floatability damage
11	Platform rotating ability damage

To classify a particular type of damage, the system needs to have historical data of that situation, so that it can classify a new incoming event with that damage. This is known as a supervised situation, whereby different healthy situations are known (i.e., It has previously occurred, and the system has “learnt” how the platforms behaves) and a new event could be classified to one of those situations with a certain probability. Currently, if different damages have a similar ‘symptom’, then they cannot be differentiated between.

In early operation, the SHM system will be building up data of the ‘healthy state’ and is unlikely to be able to indicate any damages with a high degree of reliability. The baseline inspection discussed in Section 7 is therefore important to confirm fitness for service in the first year. After the first year of operation the SHM should have enough data from which to define ‘healthy’ and ‘unhealthy’ situations. When the SHM System flags an ‘unhealthy’ state, this should be investigated with an inspection as soon as possible. If this occurs, it should be considered by the operator as to whether it would be appropriate to coincide with other inspections as per the inspection plan, to optimise the use of resources. For example, if there is an inspection scheduled in 4 months, this should be brought forward to coincide with the inspection due to the ‘unhealthy’ SHM system warning (see Section 11.3 above for further guidance on optimising inspection frequency).

Later in operation, e.g., 10 years and beyond, the SHM will have hopefully built up enough data to potentially start classifying damages, including their location and mechanisms of degradation. In this instance, mitigation, intervention and/or repair measures can be implemented immediately without the need for inspection.

16. Summary

Current IM practices for mooring systems are expensive and unsuitable for floating offshore wind farms. A risk-based IM strategy for MooringSense has been developed, with the aim of reducing OPEX and increasing efficiency of FOWT. The strategy targets inspection efforts on high-risk degradation mechanisms, assessed on their likelihood of failure and consequence of failure.

A risk assessment and inspection plan according to the risk and type of degradation has been developed.

The strategy utilises the MooringSense digital twin as part of the risk assessment process, using data from the remaining useful life tool and SHM system.

17. References

1. *Risk Based Inspection, API Recommended Practice 580*. s.l. : **American Petroleum Institute, First Edition, May 2002.**
2. Gallego, Aitor. *D2.3 Version 2.0 FOW Reference Case and Set up of the Baseline*. 2020.

